

Semantic Classification of Ornithonyms in Uzbek and English Languages

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Abstract:

This article is about semantic classification of ornithonyms in Uzbek and English languages and about semantic groups, which can be divided into five groups as natural ornithonyms, mythological ornithonyms, artistic ornithonyms, ornithonyms with religious content and ornithonyms with symbolic meaning.

Keywords: natural ornithonyms, mythological ornithonyms, artistic ornithonyms, ornithonyms with religious content, ornithonyms with symbolic meaning, Humo, Qaqnus, Semurg, Owlman, Phoenix, Rain Bird, Oozlum bird.

Birds began to form in the human mind during the earliest imaginations. As an active unit of nature, birds have attracted the attention of man. Birds are regarded as food for humans, a component of living nature and sometimes as a symbol of the existence of life. From their flight to the north or beyond the ocean, they learned that there is land and life on that side.

Ornithonyms can be semantically divided into different semantic groups:

1. natural ornithonyms, 2) mythological ornithonyms, 3) artistic ornithonyms,
2. ornithonyms with religious content, 5) ornithonyms with symbolic meaning.

Natural ornithonyms refer to the names of birds that exist in nature. Examples of natural ornithonyms in the Uzbek language are *burgut*, *chumchuq*, *bulbul*, *qarg'a*, *kalxat* (eagle, sparrow, nightingale, crow, hawk). In English, there are ornithonyms such as crow, falcon, dove, hawk.

Mythological ornithonyms refer to the names of birds of a mythical nature that do not exist in nature. For example, ornithonyms such as Semurg, Anqo, Xumo.

Artistic ornithonyms are mostly invented by creators and used in the text of works in the form of a bird. For example, in Uzbek *omad qushi*, *baxt qushi*, *tole' qushi*, *iqbol qushi* and in English bluebird, mandarin duck, etc.

Bird names with religious meaning have a completely separate meaning. They exist in life and are mentioned in religious texts. For example, in the "Elephant" chapter of the Holy Qur'an, there is information about how birds of *Abobil* destroyed the army of Qadaha, who were coming to destroy the Kaaba in the Islamic religion, by throwing clay fragments.

Among the birds, which are one of the most amazing wonders of living nature, there is a family of birds belonging to the family of sparrows known as birds of paradise (Paradisaeidae). The smallest representative of this family is the king bird of paradise, its length is fifteen centimeters and its weight is about fifty grams. The largest representative, the silent monocodia, is forty-four centimeters long and weighs four hundred and thirty grams. Charles Darwin's friend Alfred Russel Wallace spent 6 years living and studying the zoogeographic region of Australia and wrote his famous book "The Malay Archipelago" (1869) in which he provided a lot of information about birds of paradise. Since the feathers of birds of paradise are extremely beautiful, there has been great interest in hunting them since ancient times. This, in turn, led to a decrease in the number of species and individuals of birds, and a sharp reduction in the area of their habitat. Currently, many species of birds of paradise are included in the International Red Book, and their hunting is prohibited. In 1825, the English ornithologist William John Swainson presented a family of birds of paradise called "Paradisaeidae".

In addition, the image of a bird is widely covered in religious concepts. It is written that people with a bird's heart will enter heaven. Words meaning the names of birds are usually included in the series of concrete nouns and are units that denote the names of objectively existing things. Among them, there are also words denoting the names of mythical birds, which mean the names of birds that do not exist in objective existence, but are mentioned only in myths and created in the imagination. Such bird names can be found in mythology and folk poetry. Humo bird, Semurg, Anqo, Qaqnus and others are examples of these.

In ancient times, people used to create legends about miraculous birds. Birds have been a symbol of people's dreams since time immemorial, and their flight in the sky and flapping of their wings probably aroused a feeling of envy in people. Since legends are the product of free creativity of people, they have a wide opportunity for creative images and imagination. This factor plays a big role in the creation of myths. Some bird names are mentioned among mythonyms. Mythical birds do not exist in objective existence, but are created in imagination as an example of people's pursuit of happiness and perfection. Flight is the eternal dream of man, and it is the main reason for the formation of mythological characters in birds. Humo, Semurg, Anqo, Qaqnus are examples of mythonyms denoting the names of birds. These lexemes are defined in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" as follows: Humo is a Persian name of a legendary bird that is a symbol of goodness. It is a legendary bird that is believed to land on the head or its shadow, that person will be the happiest and will achieve the state and kingdom; bird of happiness, "state bird". In Eastern mythology, the image of Humo bird is a symbol of happiness, state, and the sources describe that its head is made of gold and its wings are made of silver. The bird represented by the word Humo did not exist, it was created in the imagination of people. Because the existence of a bird with a head made of gold and wings made of silver, and the image of flying and landing on someone's head, confirms that the word is mythological in nature. Humo bird is a symbol of happiness and goodness, so it is also accepted as a state symbol.

“Semurgh - Persian thirty birds: the name of a legendary bird, a legendary bird in the oral poetic works of the peoples of the East.” The word “Semurg” is the name of a bird described in legends, and it appeared in the works of Alisher Navoi as a mythological character. The name of this bird,

which means passing bird (si (thirty) + bird (bird)) in Persian, is used in a figurative sense and served to express the image of the creator in the work "Lison ut-tayr". The word Semurg means a very large legendary bird, it is said that the wings of this bird are made of gold, and its throne is excellent. This word is also considered to have a mythological character.

"Anqo is a legendary big bird (used as a symbol of absence) that supposedly lived on Mount Qaf." Qaqnus is the name of a legendary bird, which lives in forests and grasslands. This word is not explained in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language". According to legends, a bird of prey comes out of the thickets and gathers sticks, twigs and wood in its beak and creates a big fire. It burns in this fire. From the embers and ashes of the burning fire, the child of Qaqnus comes out and repeats his mother's actions. This story, told in the legend, is an expression of the philosophy of life, it reflects the meaning, action and end of a person's life, the duration of life, the repetition of traditions in generations. Qaqnus bird is an image of a mythological character, and this word embodies the image of a bird based only on imagination. Qaqnus is also mentioned in the works of Alisher Navoi, the thinker effectively used folk poetic examples in his work. The use of the names of animals and birds in the text of myths, or the transformation of people into animals or birds, is one of the main themes of mythology and reflects the inseparable organic relationship between man and nature. Myths serve to reflect these meanings.

Names of birds that represent mythonomic concepts also contain signs of positivity. Among them, birds such as Semurg and Humo are said to bring happiness, happiness, and state in myths, and according to the imagination that whoever these birds land on, will bring kingdom, state, and happiness, a positive evaluation tone is formed in relation to these names.

Oxunjon, saodat ertak emasdir,

Ehtimol, dunyoda humolar bordir. (O.Hakimov. «Dunyo, Dunyo...»

8-page).

In the example, it is used as a bird that brings happiness and good luck, referring to the idea expressed in the text of fairy tales and legends.

Qay yurtning bor seningdayin Sinolari, Humolari

Agar unga etay desang, Xalq bo'l, elim! (M.Yusuf).

In this example, the word "Humo" is used both as a bird that brings happiness and as a reference to the expression on the national emblem of Uzbekistan.

A number of legendary bird names are also mentioned in English. For example: Owlman, Phoenix, Rain Bird, Cetan, etc. In the table below, we can see some legendary bird names. Legendary bird names and their definitions:

Name of mythical birds	Features
Adarna	has healing powers, put people to sleep, and turn people into stone
Aethon	eagle tormentor of Prometheus
Alkonost	female with body of a bird
Alectryon	rooster

«In Cornish folklore, the *Owlman* (Cornish: *Cowanden*), sometimes referred to as the Cornish Owlman, or the Owlman of Mawnan, is an owl-like humanoid creature said to have been seen in 1976 in the village of Mawnan, Cornwall, UK. The Owlman is sometimes compared to the American Mothman legend from mid 1960s; however, a Eurasian eagle-owl is likely the source of the legend».

«*The phoenix* is an immortal bird associated with Greek mythology (with analogs in many cultures such as Egyptian and Persian) that cyclically regenerates or is otherwise born again. Associated with the sun, a phoenix obtains new life by rising from the ashes of its predecessor. Some legends say it dies in a show of flames and combustion, others that it simply dies and decomposes before being born again...The Latin word comes from Greek φοῖνιξ *phoinīx*. The Greek word is first attested in the Mycenaean Greek po-ni-ke, which probably meant «griffin», though it might have meant «palm tree». That word is probably a borrowing from a West Semitic word for madder, a red dye made from *Rubia tinctorum*. The word Phoenician appears to be from the same root, meaning «those who work with red dyes». So phoenix may mean «the Phoenician bird» or «the purplish-red bird». –

«*A chattering crow lives out nine generations of aged men, but a stag's life is four times a crow's, and a raven's life makes three stags old, while the phoenix outlives nine ravens, but we, the rich-haired Nymphs, daughters of Zeus the aegis-holder, outlive ten phoenixes*». (The Great Works, 75 page)

«The *oozlum* bird, also spelled *ouzelum*, is a legendary creature found in Australian and British folk tales and legends. Some versions have it that, when startled, the bird will take off and fly around in ever-decreasing circles until it manages to fly up its own backside, disappearing completely, which adds to its rarity. Other sources state that the bird flies backwards so that it can admire its own beautiful tail feathers, or because while it does not know where it is going, it likes to know where it has been».

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